

VARIETIES OF BEEF AND CULINARY CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: Provide an understanding of the characteristics of beef and its use. Elucidating the energy and value of meat, the method of deodorization, boiling, frying, steaming, and all other heat treatment methods. It consists of clarifying the advantages of cooking and consumption with what products.

Keywords: meat, loin, fat, muscle tissue, breast, breast, thigh, shoulder, back, thigh, leg, rump, etc.

The relevance of the topic: Beef is, without exaggeration, the most popular and healthy meat we eat. It is not very fatty, so it is a dietary product and has several important properties. Meat provides the human body with digestible animal proteins, fats, and carbohydrates. 100 g of boiled meat included in a person's daily diet provides 200 calories. This is already half of the amount of protein needed by the body. Nutrients of meat are concentrated mainly in its muscle tissue, to a lesser extent in fatty tissue, and very little in connective tissue. Therefore, the less connective tissue in meat, the higher its nutritional value. Today, cattle are raised on natural pastures in almost all countries of the world:

Holland, New Zealand, Denmark, Argentina, Italy, Uzbekistan, Ukraine, and, of course, Russia. Both large enterprises and farms are engaged in agriculture. The only country where it is forbidden to eat cows is India - where the animal is considered sacred.

Classification of cattle: Cattle are divided into several categories: dairy, beef, and dual purpose. The most popular meat breeds: are Kazakh white head, Hereford, Aberdeen-Angus, Kalmyk, and Shorthorn, combined cattle: Simmental, Swiss, Kostroma, and other breeds. In beef carcasses, the optimal ratio between meat and fat (more precisely, between protein and fat) is 1: 1, in pork - 1: 2.5 . The quality of meat depends not only on the total amount of fat but also on the location of its concentration. Adipose tissues are mainly located on the surface of the meat and are not evaluated from the point of view of cooking. The highest quality, juicy, and tender meat with layers of fat inside the muscle is called marble meat. Marble beef is famous for its nutritional value - this category is represented by the meat of young calves up to 18-20 months. Meat is widely used in cooking and is the basis of many traditional dishes today. We will tell you in our article. In addition, depending on the age of the cattle and the fat content of the product, three categories are distinguished: first, second, and third, which is called lean beef. You can see what category the meat belongs to by the seal.

Although different countries cut meat in different ways, three types are still traditionally distinguished:

- High grade includes back, chest, buttock, buttock, shoulder, and thigh.
- The first type includes: the shoulder blade, chest, and side
- The second type includes the neck, tail, front, the lower part of the legs from the jumping joint, and back caps.

In total, it is divided into 10 to 14 pieces, and each of them has its characteristics and purpose in cooking. The chemical composition and nutritional value of meat affect its anatomical origin because, in different parts (cuts) of the same carcass, the main tissues have different proportions and different characteristics. Thus, in terms of the total amount of protein, fat, and moisture, the meat of the back, loin, and back parts of the carcass does not differ from the meat of the front parts - shoulder, breast, and shoulder. Leg meat has a higher total protein content and less fat than other meats. The location of the part in the meat has a greater influence on the biological properties of proteins. Forequarter cuts contained more incomplete protein than rear cuts, but significantly less than lower limb cuts.

Culinary feature of beef: The best meat for processing in the kitchen is meat with 17% protein, 20% fat, 62% water, and 1% ash. Different types of meat differ in their chemical composition and calorie content. According to scientific data, the highest-calorie meat is lamb (142-351 calories) and pork (130-406 calories). The nutritional value of beef is 105-285 calories, horse meat - 162. Beef (17.5-21.0 percent), followed by lamb (15.3- 20 percent) and pork (14.5-21.6 percent).

Beef is an important supplier of protein and amino acids, has a high nutritional value, is quickly digested, and gives a feeling of fullness without blocking the body with various "wastes". The product is useful due to its high mineral content, rich in zinc and iron. It is the basis of a healthy menu and is indispensable in the diet of athletes, children, pregnant and lactating women, as well as in therapeutic and dietary nutrition. Veal meat is more highly valued, it is softer, has less coarse fiber, and the fat layer is represented by unsaturated fatty acids. Beef is useful after operations, during significant blood loss, restoration, and maintenance of immunity.

Beef has a distinct meaty taste and a pleasant aroma of meat and milk. Older cattle have a stronger smell, color, and taste. But anything can change the taste of the product: animal breed, age, feed, storage conditions, and correct organization of the washing technique are of great importance. As the age and fatness of animals increases, the amount of moisture and protein in the meat decreases, the amount of fat increases, and the amount of calories increases. The meat of well-fed animals is characterized by the necessary composition and quality of proteins and fats. The amount of glycogen in the muscles also decreases dramatically. The chemical composition and calorie content of meat depends on the animal's fatness. Type I lamb meat contains 13.9 percent protein, and 16 percent fat, and the nutritional value is 206 calories, while beef contains 15.2, 9.9, and 154 calories, respectively. The nutritional value of fatty pork reaches 381 calories. Compared to lean veal, it has 4 times the nutritional value considering

that it has only 74 calories. The nutritional value of pork (245 calories) is higher than grade I beef (154 calories), grade II lamb (151 calories), and even lean veal (131 calories). The nutritional value of the meat of older animals is much higher than that of young animals, due to the presence of a large amount of complete proteins. However, after cooking, the meat of a young animal is softer and easier to digest. Therefore, young animal meat is used to prepare dishes that require short heat treatment - kebabs, and natural cutlets. Therefore, choosing quality meat is a responsible process. In appearance, it should be elastic, bright, and have a natural red color. The oil is soft, almost without films. If the product does not have a natural smell, it means that the meat is of poor quality or not fresh at all. You should not freeze beef, the flavor and aroma will become less intense during the freezing process and then completely disappear.

Beef is widely used in the food industry and cooking. Meat is very suitable for heat treatment, frying, boiling, baking, marinating, grilling, drying, smoking, and all other types of processing. The composition of boiled meat largely depends on the fat content of the animal and the amount of fat in individual pieces. Estimated cooking losses range from 1.6 percent (thin beef) to 54.5 percent (large beef), averaging 15 to 35 percent by weight. The chemical composition of raw and cooked meat is different. Boiled meat has a high protein content. Raw beef has an average of 21 percent protein, boiled beef has 30 percent, veal has 22 and 27 percent, lamb has 19 and 26 percent, and pork has it will be 14 and 18 percent.

The amount of fat in boiled beef, veal, and lamb is slightly higher than in raw meat (1-2%). The amount of fat in raw pork is 31 percent, and in cooked pork is 38.7 percent. The amount of ash in cooked meat is slightly reduced (0.1-0.2%). When frying meat, the front part of the breast is well-fried. Beef is very tough meat, so it is recommended to use different marinades. To get a rich broth, you need to boil the meat in cold water. To preserve the maximum amount of substances, the meat should be put in boiling water and cooked for about 1.5 hours.

Before cooking beef, it is recommended to remove it from the refrigerator in advance so that the meat can rest at room temperature. Prick the meat with a skewer to check for doneness. If the juice is red, the meat is bloody, if it is pink, the meat is medium-rare. Clear juice indicates that the meat is well cooked. After cooking, leave the meat for 10 minutes, so that the juices are evenly distributed, and only then cut. When cooking beef, you can add sour cream or mayonnaise, which will make the meat juicy and tender. Other cooks just add soda. However, this method requires the use of a vessel with high walls, as baking soda will boil when it comes into contact with hot water. It is recommended to use kiwi as a softener. To do this, you need to cut the beef into pieces and then mix it with the peeled fruits. After exactly fifteen minutes, the meat product should be removed from the fruit and subjected to further cooking. To make the meat tender, you can completely soak the beef in kefir and put it in the refrigerator overnight.

Deodorizing Beef: Four proven methods are recommended for deodorizing beef:

Wine. Place a piece of beef in a deep dish, fill it with red wine, and add rosemary and thyme. Put the container with meat in the refrigerator for an hour. When the time is up, remove the beef from the wine and continue cooking.

Mustard. To do this, you need to generously coat the beef with mustard, put it in a bowl, and put it in the refrigerator for several hours. Then the meat should

be washed under running water and the delicacy used for further production.

Potassium permanganate. You need to make a light pink solution, dip the beef in it, and put it in the refrigerator for one hundred and twenty minutes. Then the product should be washed under water.

Chamomile decoction. First, you need to prepare chamomile, and then you need to filter the broth. Then put the beef in clean broth, add a little sugar, and leave for about twenty minutes. Then the meat should be washed in salted water.

Summary: Delicious meatballs, meatballs, dumplings, sausages, and other dishes are prepared from ground beef. It makes excellent first courses, clear broths, and soups. For them, you can use parts of the shoulder and ribs, ham, ham on the bone, and sugar bone. Great cutlets, gimbal meat, and kebabs are prepared from breast and thigh meat. Meat often becomes a component of delicious salads. Beef can be served with grains, pasta, and vegetables. It goes well with spices: coriander, cumin, bay leaf, black and red pepper. In a word, beef is the most convenient meat for daily consumption.

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